
LINGUOCULTURAL ANALYSIS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES: THE PROBLEM OF EQUIVALENCE

Valieva Nargizakhon Zamir kizi

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Annotation: This study investigates the linguocultural characteristics and translation challenges of phraseological units (PhUs) in English and Russian, with a focus on the problem of equivalence. Through a comparative analysis, the study identifies varying degrees of equivalence—full, partial, and zero equivalence—encountered when translating culturally bound PhUs between English and Russian. The study examines translation techniques such as literal translation, adaptation, and omission, evaluating their effectiveness in preserving both linguistic and cultural integrity.

Keywords: phraseology, culture, phraseological units, linguocultural analysis, equivalence in translation.

Phraseological units (PhUs) play a crucial role in any language, as they encapsulate unique cultural, historical, and social elements specific to the people who use them. These expressions often go beyond the sum of their individual words, providing insights into the values, beliefs, and collective experiences of a linguistic community. When studying PhUs in English and Russian, a linguocultural analysis becomes invaluable, as it allows researchers to uncover how each language reflects its respective culture’s worldview. The complexity of these units poses challenges, particularly when one seeks to translate them across languages with distinct cultural backgrounds. The difficulty of translating PhUs lies in the cultural specificity embedded within them, which may lack a direct equivalent in the target language. Consequently, this study addresses the need for a deeper understanding of

phraseological equivalence and the challenges it presents in English-Russian translation.

The primary goal of this research is to examine the linguistic and cultural nuances present in English and Russian phraseological units and explore how they influence the translation process. By identifying both equivalent and non-equivalent expressions, the study aims to shed light on how closely PhUs in these two languages can be aligned or differ due to cultural distinctions.

Phraseological units (PhUs) are stable, multi-word expressions whose meanings cannot be derived from the literal meanings of their constituent parts. They are unique linguistic phenomena that often include idioms, collocations, and set phrases. In both English and Russian, PhUs reflect cultural references, social values, and historical experiences, which makes them a rich area for linguocultural analysis.

Equivalence in translation refers to the degree to which a translated phrase accurately conveys the meaning, style, and cultural context of the original text. In the context of PhUs, achieving equivalence can be particularly challenging due to the cultural specificity embedded within these expressions. Different types of equivalence are important to consider:

Semantic Equivalence: This type aims to preserve the meaning of the original PhU as closely as possible. While semantic equivalence maintains conceptual accuracy, it may require the translator to adapt certain cultural references.

Functional Equivalence: Here, the emphasis is on preserving the function or communicative effect of the original PhU. Even if the expression differs in structure or specific imagery, it should evoke a similar reaction in the target language.

Cultural Equivalence: This involves substituting a PhU in the source language with one from the target language that has an equivalent cultural resonance. Although this approach may diverge from the literal meaning, it allows the PhU to carry similar cultural implications, aiding understanding for the target audience.

The linguocultural approach to phraseology examines the interconnectedness of language and culture, emphasizing how cultural values, historical contexts, and worldviews shape language use. PhUs are particularly well-suited to this approach

because they often embody cultural concepts, idiomatic meanings, and metaphors unique to a given language community. In English and Russian, for example, many PhUs are rooted in folklore, historical events, or social practices unique to each culture. By using a linguocultural approach, this study seeks to uncover the underlying cultural values that shape the use and interpretation of PhUs in these two languages, making it possible to identify points of cultural convergence and divergence.

Phraseological units (PhUs) serve as mirrors of cultural values, social norms, and historical contexts within any language. English and Russian PhUs reflect the unique worldviews and societal norms that have developed in these linguistic communities. For example, in English, the phrase "to break the ice" is widely understood as taking the initiative to ease social tension, especially in unfamiliar situations. This phrase traces back to literal ice-breaking activities that allowed ships to move, symbolizing the importance of initiative in individualistic and task-oriented Western culture. In Russian, the phrase "пыль в глаза пускать" ("to throw dust in the eyes") conveys the idea of deceiving or impressing others superficially, a reflection of a cultural tendency to view appearances critically.

These PhUs demonstrate how each language encapsulates distinct cultural insights. English tends to emphasize action and pragmatism, while Russian often reflects a more guarded or cautious approach to appearances and intentions. In translating such units, these cultural nuances pose significant challenges, as the translator must decide whether to prioritize literal meaning or cultural resonance.

When translating PhUs between English and Russian, varying levels of equivalence emerge. Each category highlights the challenges in maintaining both linguistic and cultural integrity:

Full Equivalence: Some English and Russian PhUs share identical meanings and similar imagery, allowing for direct translation. For instance, "to kill two birds with one stone" is closely paralleled by the Russian "убить двух зайцев одним выстрелом" ("to kill two hares with one shot"). Both expressions convey the idea of achieving multiple goals with a single action and hold similar cultural implications.

Partial Equivalence: In many cases, the concepts may align, but the cultural imagery or specifics vary, requiring the translator to adapt the expression. The English phrase "to add fuel to the fire" is used similarly in Russian as "подливать масла в огонь" ("to pour oil into the fire"), but while the concepts match, slight adjustments may be necessary to fit the idiomatic tone of each language.

Zero Equivalence: Some PhUs have no direct equivalent in the other language, particularly those with deep cultural or historical roots. For instance, the Russian phrase "ездить как сыр в масле" ("to roll like cheese in butter") has no exact English counterpart but roughly translates to "to live in comfort," referring to an ideal, carefree life. Translators often have to choose between a descriptive translation or finding a culturally resonant phrase in English that captures the concept, if not the exact imagery.

These varying levels of equivalence underscore the difficulty of conveying both the conceptual meaning and cultural context in translation, often requiring creative solutions to bridge the gap between languages.

To handle the cultural nuances of PhUs, translators employ several techniques:

Literal Translation: Translating PhUs word-for-word can work if both the meaning and cultural connotations remain intact, such as in the example of "to kill two birds with one stone." However, literal translation can sometimes distort the intended meaning or fail to convey the underlying cultural associations.

Adaptation: This technique involves substituting the original PU with a culturally resonant expression in the target language. For instance, the Russian "как две капли воды" ("like two drops of water") is typically adapted as "like two peas in a pod" in English. This allows the translator to preserve the meaning while aligning the imagery with target-language norms.

Omission: In cases where cultural references are too specific to be understood or lack relevance in the target culture, translators might omit or replace the PU with a simpler explanation. For example, a complex Russian PU deeply rooted in folklore may be simplified to ensure clarity for an English-speaking audience, though this risks losing the cultural essence.

In cases where direct translation could alter the intended meaning or cultural relevance, translators must make nuanced choices. For example, translating "показать кузькину мать" (literally, "to show Kuzka's mother") directly into English loses the idiomatic meaning of threatening or intimidating someone. Adapting it to "show someone who's boss" captures the sense of dominance without the literal folklore reference, thus retaining functional equivalence.

This study highlights the complex nature of achieving equivalence when translating phraseological units (PhUs) between English and Russian. Phraseological units embody cultural values, social norms, and historical contexts, making them significant yet challenging elements to translate. Our analysis reveals that varying levels of equivalence—full, partial, and zero equivalence—arise in translation, depending on the degree of cultural overlap. Full equivalence, while straightforward, is relatively rare, while partial and zero equivalence are common due to cultural distinctions. The study demonstrates that translators must make nuanced decisions to balance linguistic accuracy with cultural fidelity, often adapting or omitting culturally bound elements to make PhUs comprehensible and relevant in the target language.

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